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Psychological and ethical issues relating to medication non-adherence in patients with chronic disease

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ABSTRACT

Treatment or medication non-adherence (MNA) is a far-reaching challenge to clinical practise that has a significant negative impact on treatment effectiveness and compromises the health and economic outcomes for both individuals and society. Lack of adherence to recommended therapeutic regimens reduces the effectiveness of treatment and may subsequently lead to disease progression, disabilities or death. Many studies have emphasized the magnitude of MNA and its effect on treatment outcomes, the patient's health, on healthcare professionals and the associated costs. However, non-adherence is still common in clinical practice and no significant changes have been reported in recent years despite various research studies attempting to address and highlight the issue. MNA remains a major concern that is highly prevalent amongst medication-taking patients with chronic disease. Among the reported factors that may result in MNA practices are socioeconomic-related factors, factors related to the healthcare system, patient- or disease-related factors and treatment-related factors. The importance of ethical interventions cannot be understated and as such, MNA can be seen to be a multi-dimensional phenomenon which requires a far-reaching and multi-targeted solution. Several key areas in improving the rates of medication adherence are discussed and future foci in this area of research are identified.

Keywords: adherence, chronic disease, ethics, medication, psychological

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) [1] has defined treatment adherence as “the extent to which a person’s behaviour taking medication, following a diet, and/or executing lifestyle changes, corresponds with agreed recommendations from a healthcare provider”. The term does not carry the same meaning as compliance; where adherence refers to an active choice of the patient to follow through with the prescribed treatment and taking responsibility for their own well-being, compliance is a passive approach in which the patient is following the physician’s instructions [2, 3].

The efficacy of any therapeutic regimen depends on the adherence of the patient involved. However, medication non-adherence with the associated adverse effects is becoming more prevalent among patients with chronic diseases where research suggests that up to 50% or more patients undergoing long-term treatment for a somatic disorder either do not take their medications in as prescribed or cease taking them altogether [4].

Chronic disease refers to medical conditions that require long-term treatment and are often associated with increased mortality and morbidity and have been shown to be the leading cause of death globally. Chronic disease prevalence is increasing worldwide and patients with chronic diseases require long-term maintenance use of medications [5]. Non-adherence to prescribed medication is estimated to result in at least 100 000 preventable deaths and billions of dollars in preventable medical costs per annum. However, not only do physicians have limited time in order to detect patients with a poor adherence but recent studies suggest that health professionals appear to either ignore medication non-adherence or regard it as a patient problem and not a clinician or health system issue [6, 7].

The results of non-adherence to treatment regimens may encompass a deterioration of the patient’s condition, impairment of the effectiveness of the treatment, and may negatively affect the patient’s response to future interventions. The wider outcomes of non-adherence include the increased need for hospitalization, negative effects on overall quality of life, symptom recurrence, heightened comorbidities and the overextension of healthcare resources [8]. Identifying the reasons for non-adherence is critical in order to customize interventions [9].

2. MEDICATION NON ADHERENCE

Medication use is a complex behaviour and potentially influencing factors have been researched and proven to be associated with it. The results suggest that demographic, medical, and personality factors are less influential on adherence than are psychological and emotional aspects [10]. Non-adherence may be defined as the interactions between the individual and a specific treatment, within a social and environmental context and encompasses a complex interplay of factors involving patients, caregivers, healthcare providers, and the health system. MNA comprises a behavioural continuum which ranges from outright refusal to use prescribed medication or completely non-adherent behaviour, through partial adherence to treatment regimens to correct and regular medication use. The most common forms of MNA include failure to fill prescriptions, delaying the start of treatment, unintentional/ intentional omission of individual doses, regular alteration of dosing frequency, breaks in drug administration lasting longer than a few days, or early discontinuation of therapy [2;4].

The traditional medical model, which assumes that medical treatment grounded on scientific evidence is optimal for the patient, and that the proven effectiveness of treatment is sufficient motivation for the patient to comply, does not adequately explain MNA. It presupposes that the only obstacles to adherence may be socioeconomic factors such as gender, age and education, without consideration for the influence of the patient's subjective perspective of disease-related factors, including knowledge about the origins of the disease and its progression, the individual's views on medication, the perceived efficacy and side effects or the doctor-patient relationship or the patient's life circumstances [4].

Thus, adherence can be seen as a product of both motivation and capability. In these terms motivation comprises the individual's conscious decision-making processes whereas capability comprises both the physical and psychological skills required to adhere to the treatment regimen. Motivation and capability may be influenced by social and environmental factors which may in turn inform the opportunity to adhere in response to either internal cues such as experiencing symptoms or external cues such as receiving a reminder [11].

Environmental challenges within the healthcare system including limited access to healthcare, high costs, inadequate instructions and insufficient patient education may hamper medication adherence. Conversely, patient-related factors may include unintentional lapses in medication use which is particularly prevalent with complex medication regimens and intentional non-adherence motivated by economic, health-belief, adverse effects or expectation-related reasons [9].

MNA can be classified as primary and secondary MNA. Primary non-adherence is defined as an instance where a patient fails to fill a new prescription and thus does not commence the medication regimen as prescribed by the healthcare provider. Secondary non-adherence is describes a patient who fills a prescription but does not use the medication as prescribed. Although many reasons for non-adherence exist, they can be further subdivided into two categories: unintentional and intentional. Cases where patients try to adhere to the prescribed course of treatment but are hampered by their circumstances are regarded as unintentional non-adherence (UNA). Forgetting to take a medication, having difficulty with using it, being unable to afford the medication or having difficulty understanding the directions are instances of UNA. Intentional non-adherence (INA) refers to cases where patients make the choice not to adhere to treatment instructions. Research suggests that this may be the result of several factors: concerns regarding adverse side-effects, doubts surrounding the efficacy of the medication, health belief systems or personal convictions that are in contradiction with the recommended course of treatment, or the opinion that the prescription is unnecessary [12;13].

3. PSYCHOLOGICAL PREDICTORS OF MNA

The psychological predictors of MNA are not broadly covered in the literature. These refer specifically to the subjective factors that affect the way individuals perceive, interpret and cope with reality. These factors influence decision-making and motivational processes which impact the response to medical recommendation [14].

A recent study identified three important factors relating to the predictors of adherence. The findings suggest the strongest predictor of adherence is the individual's style of coping with stress. As chronic disease commonly leads to psychological stress, the patient's coping strategy affects co-operation with medical management.

A task-oriented style is strongly associated with a more adherent response, with more active coping strategies such as seeking information about the disease and the therapy involved. Conversely, an emotional style reflects attempts to cope with the stress through emotional responses such as anger, blame or rumination and is associated with higher levels of MNA. An avoidance style refers to the use of distraction and withdrawal to avoid stress which is also maladaptive [4].

A further significant factor in treatment adherence is the individual's own approach to health and the belief that the treatment is appropriate and justified, or health locus of control (HLOC). A recent study found that locus of control is another strong predictor of MNA. HLOC consists of three subtypes: the internal health locus of control (IHLOC), external health locus of control (EHLOC) and chance health locus of control (CHLOC). IHLOC refers to the extent to which the individual believes that their actions and their own agency are responsible for their disease and health, while EHLOC refers to those individuals who believe that powerful others, such as their physicians, have control over their health. Those individuals who believe that chance or luck informs their health have a CHLOC.

Studies show that individuals with higher IHLOC are more likely to engage in self-management behaviour and more frequently undertake pro-wellbeing actions to prevent disease than those with EHLOC or CHLOC. However, in the context of MNA, IHLOC is considered a negative factor as some studies show that it is common for individuals who believe they have influence on their own health to be less likely to comply with treatment recommendations when compared to people with EHLOC [14-16].

In particular, IHLOC was positively associated with patient modification of their prescribed drug regime without consulting their physician [17]. However there is some disparity in the literature with other recent studies finding that IHLOC predicted greater treatment adherence [18-20].

Further, some research suggests that a high degree of medication adherence was associated with the belief that health status is determined by chance. Patients in long-term treatment may tend to relinquish responsibility for the therapeutic process and that after some time on medication, they may experience fatigue and become discouraged. The belief in chance as the source of therapeutic success may be a defence mechanism which would allow them to free themselves and their physician from the responsibility for any potential treatment failure [14].

HLOC is generally a stable construct, therefore evaluating an individual's HLC may assist in identifying those individuals who are more likely to engage in or adhere to self-management behaviours [4].

Research has demonstrated that mindfulness is also a significant factor influencing adherence. Mindfulness is a modifiable factor which relates to the individual's awareness of emotions and the ability to interpret somatic signals and represents conscious and non-judgmental attention to the present moment. The correlation of mindfulness and health, including adherence with medication treatment, has been confirmed in patients with chronic disease. Recent studies suggest a relationship between mindfulness and higher disease acceptance, a higher level of adherence to medication recommendations and thus a better quality of life in chronic diseases [21].

Some studies suggest that the personality traits of agreeableness and conscientiousness predict greater treatment adherence, whereas the traits of neuroticism predicted lower treatment adherence. Extraversion and openness did not predict treatment adherence. [20].

HLC and coping styles are relatively stable constructs so it is crucial that physicians are conscious of these factors in relation to each patient and utilise appropriate interventions when recommending therapeutic approaches to the patient. Mindfulness is a psychological factor which can be developed through exercise and training, and may improve adherence by increasing attention to health, sleep, stress and mood and has potential in providing patient support throughout the treatment process [4].

4. OTHER FACTORS INFLUENCING MNA

Recent studies suggest that several other psychosocial factors play a role in MNA. It was found that higher perceived social support is most consistently associated with adherence. The findings suggest that social support might contribute to greater patient adherence by increasing their confidence in their ability to perform and adhere to positive health behaviours and can thus have significant clinical consequences [22].

Moreover, the specific type of social support is associated with improved medication adherence. Social support utilization or the extent to which patients can utilize and receive support has been linked to improved medication adherence among diabetic patients whereas functional social support or the degree of emotional support, information and encouragement patients get from their social network has been associated with better medication adherence in hypertensive patients.

This confirms the importance of implementing strategies to improve social support to increase medication adherence and improve health outcomes for patients with chronic conditions [23].

Furthermore, recent studies suggest that chronic patients with relatively less knowledge about their medications are significantly correlated with MNA and that side effects and the absence of chronic medication counselling are equally significant [5]. Understanding the reasons for the necessity of medications that were prescribed and being informed of medication side effects were also found to influence medication adherence [24].

It is commonly accepted that gender may influence medication adherence. Recent research suggests that male patients are associated with better adherence and with lower risk of medication discontinuation and higher persistence independent of age and medication type. However no difference emerged when patients with worse comorbidity status and taking drug combinations were compared [25]. Other studies confirm that female patients experience adherence problems more often than males, particularly in terms of discontinuation and cost-related nonadherence [26, 27].

Older age was a significant predictor of greater adherence to prescribed medications which suggests that older patients may be more aware of the benefits of medication on their symptoms [24]. Age and years since diagnosis were significantly associated with the level of medication adherence in elderly patients [28]. A recent study identified older adults with multimorbidity, a lower education level, higher medication self-efficacy, better social support and no side effects as exhibiting greater medication adherence [29].

Research has demonstrated that medical adherence is higher in urban dwellers and those with a stronger relationship with their physicians. These patients followed their medication recommendations to a greater extent than those living in rural areas as they report problems with access to and organization of medical services as reasons for MNA [4, 30].

5. ETHICAL ISSUES IN MNA

The ethics of adherence implies a conflict within the definition of adherence. Evidence-based medicine appears to provide clear directives for clinical decisions but often the patient is not part of these decision-making processes. Clinicians may independently develop a treatment plan and then attempt to make the therapy sufficiently acceptable to the patient to achieve adherence. Interventions are tested to influence patient behaviour, but frequently are not designed to consider the patient's point of view. The individual's perspective and goals, their culture and wishes will affect their adherence with a medical treatment plan and it is crucial that the patient shares in these decisions. The most ethical decisions in medicine occur when the physician and patient both contribute to the treatment process and the recognition of the individuality and autonomy of the patient appears to be the most ethical approach to medical treatment decisions. The attitudes and interpersonal qualities of physicians towards patients play a vital role in the struggle for improved adherence with medical therapies [31].

6. STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING MEDICATION ADHERENCE

Patient adherence is a complex issue leading to huge burden on our healthcare system. Understanding the magnitude and scope of the problem of MNA is a vital step in reaching better adherence rates. A recent study identified several key factors in adherence-enhancing strategies.

- simplification of the treatment regimen to match the patient's daily activities
- imparting knowledge regarding the patient's condition and possible interventions
- modifying the patient's perceptions and tailoring treatment
- patient and family communication, support and care
- adapting patient education to their level of understanding
- evaluating the level of adherence through self-reports

This approach views adherence is a dynamic process that needs to be extensively evaluated in order to assess both the process and outcome of treatment [32].

7. CONCLUSION

With rates of chronic disease rising globally, it becomes imperative to identify the determinants of patient medication adherence and to explore novel ways of enhancing patient adherence to their treatment regimens. In many instances, patient communication, education and support have been found to be the optimal interventions in achieving this goal. Future research should further examine the range of determinants to enable more complete understanding of medication adherence and to determine how to approach those patients at higher risk of MNA most effectively. Additionally, these results could be used in the development of new interventions, or a modification of existing interventions to target those factors most strongly associated with adherence. Healthcare providers need to be keenly aware of the significance of the patient's health beliefs, the quality of their social support structures and the importance of communicating information regarding their treatment in understandable terms in the quest to improve medication adherence.

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